

ENHANCED FOG DETECTION AND FREE SPACE SEGEMENTATION FOR DRIVER IDENTIFICATION IN A VEHICLE

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ABSTRACT

Car navigation relies heavily on free space detection. Unfortunately, traditional approaches have difficulties in adverse weather conditions, particularly during the day. A solution is proposed in this paper using a contrast restoration approach on images captured by an in-vehicle camera. In several ways, the proposed method advances the state of the art. First, the fog region of interest is better segmented as a result of the computation of shortest routes maps. Second, the fog density and horizon line position are computed together. The method then restores the contrast of the road by assuming that the road is flat while also detecting vertical objects. Finally, the free space area is determined by segmenting the connected component in front of the vehicle. To predict the method's effectiveness, an experimental validation was performed. Various outcomes are shown on sample images extracted from video sequences captured by an in-vehicle camera. The proposed method is complementary to existing free space area detection methods relying on color segmentation and stereovision.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays public areas are monitored by several cameras in order to increase public order and safety. For most applications, trained and experienced human operators can do this monitoring very well. However, watching multiple camera images at the same time is not only too expensive but also practically impossible. Detection of foreground objects of interest from a surveillance video sequence is a key step for an intelligent visual surveillance system. In the literature there are various algorithms proposed for object detection. All of these approaches assume that the input images have clear visibility, thus they can achieve satisfying results under clear weather conditions. Unfortunately, this is not always true, such as when videos are taken under bad weather conditions, such as on a foggy day. The image suffers degradation and severe contrast loss. These low-quality images are a nuisance for conventional object detection algorithms.

II. EXISTING METHOD

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed model follows dark channel prior, guided filter for enhancement and saliency map for object detection. It consists of five steps.

Step 1: Collecting the test images from public database.

Step 2: Dark channel prior based transmission map was extracted for remove the haze in image. And for further enhancement, guided filter was applied for restore the dehazed image.

Step 3: The enhanced image is segmented and vehicles are detected based on saliency map.

Step 4: To avoid the accident distance was calculated between the detected object and camera mounted vehicle. Finally based on the distance, some alert system provided to driver.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

The above block diagram is explained with the help of Image Acquisition it means Images are acquired from Gallery. Image Enhancement means In this stage, image is enhanced in terms of haze removal. In our work, haze removal is implemented by using dark channel prior and guided filter. Dark channel prior is used for extract the transmission map and guided filter is proposed for smooth the transmission map. At last, we get restore dehazed image by smoothed transmission map. Vehicle Detection explained vehicle is detected by saliency map and morphological operation. The enhanced image is segmented and then vehicle was detected. After vehicle detection, distance calculation is performed between detected object and testing camera mounted vehicle. Then distance value is converted pixel into meters. Based the distance of the object from the camera mounted vehicle, three kinds of messages (indication) are given to the driver i.e., object very near, if object is very near to the vehicle, object little far, if the object is little far from the vehicle and very far, if the object is very far and at a safe distance from the vehicle.

WORKING OF HAZE REMOVAL

We propose a novel prior -dark channel prior, for single image haze removal. The dark channel prior is based on the statistics of haze-free outdoor images. We find that, in most of the local regions which do not cover the sky, it is very often that some pixels have very low intensity in at least one colour (RGB) channel. In the haze image, the intensity of these dark pixels in that channel is mainly contributed by the air-light. Therefore, these dark pixels can directly provide accurate estimation of the haze’s transmission. Combining a haze imaging model and a guided filter method, we can recover a hi-quality haze-free image and produce a good depth map (up to a scale). Our approach is physically valid and is able to handle distant objects even in the heavy haze image. We do not rely on significant variance on transmission or surface shading in the input image. The result contains few halo artifacts.

WORKING OF OBJECT DETECTION

The simplest method to obtain the salient object region is by thresholding the saliency map to get a binary mask. In order to accurately detect salient objects from saliency maps, image segmentation result is combined with the saliency map.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fog Removal

Vehicle detection

Distance calculation

V. CONCLUSION

A solution was proposed to detect the free space area in foggy road scenes thanks to a contrast restoration approach. First, the method estimates simultaneously the density of fog and the position of the horizon line in the image, which improves drastically the state of the art in this area. A highly effective fog ROI segmentation method based on geodesic maps computation is proposed as well as a novel joint fog density and horizon line estimation process.

VI. REFERENCES

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